

**PRESENT AND FUTURE OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS ON SPACE
APPLICATIONS IN THE USA**

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ABSTRACT

Space structures made from a variety of composites can be designed to meet many competing design requirements. Applications described in the presentation include: Satellites, space shuttles, space station, general earth-to orbit vehicles, and futuristic applications such as planetary surface structures, and interplanetary vehicles. The presentation emphasizes composite attributes for such applications. Specific application cases are cited where available. Current research activities and future directions are noted. The need for computational simulation methods to determine long-term behavior and the need for accelerated testing, to ascertain this behavior, are also discussed.